

1 Time scales of open-system processes in a complex and
2 heterogeneous mush-dominated plumbing system

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15 **ABSTRACT**

16 The architecture of a mush dominated plumbing system in active volcanic areas is
17 conditioning the magma pathways feeding eruptions. Open-system processes along these
18 pathways and the associated timescales are directly related to the monitoring data and the
19 eruptive behavior. Despite crystal mush-dominated systems are common in active volcanoes,
20 previous studies have not focused on the data integration of different eruptions from the mush
21 sectors, supplying a partial view of the pre-eruptive magmatic processes and hindering the
22 interpretation of the monitoring signals during unrest periods. Here we focus on the Marsili

23 seamount, where the mineral data document processes within a magmatic system vertically
24 extended throughout the local oceanic crust and made of a mush framework spotted with
25 eruptible melt- and crystal-rich pockets. We undertake a study of the Marsili olivine crystals that
26 constrains the timescales of three pre-eruptive scenarios, dominated by open-system processes:
27 (1) disaggregation of the deep Marsili Volcano mush zone occurred over a timescale of years
28 prior to the eruption; (2) rapid ascent (days) of mantle-derived basaltic magma that, in some
29 cases, intercepts shallow plagioclase-rich pockets; and (3) multiple mixing events between melt-
30 and crystal-rich mush zones occurred ca. 1-2 months and 0.5 to 3 years before the eruption. Our
31 results highlight the importance of contemporaneously studying eruptions in different locations
32 of a volcano edifice for a better comprehension on how mush-dominated plumbing systems work
33 as a whole and how this must be considered during the interpretation of monitoring data.

34 **INTRODUCTION**

35 Sub-volcanic plumbing systems are incrementally built by injections of magma from
36 depth, forming crystal mush-dominated reservoirs and rare melt-rich bodies (Marsh, 2004;
37 Cooper and Kent, 2014; Cashman et al., 2017; Ganne et al., 2018; Edmonds et al., 2019). Magma
38 pathways feeding eruptions are related to a spectrum of scenarios, ranging from deep-sourced
39 magmas rapidly ascending through the plumbing system (e.g. Albert et al., 2020) to magmas that
40 reach the surface after intercepting pre-existing magma pockets or mush zones (Nakagawa et al.,
41 2002; Cashman and Blundy, 2013; Bragagni et al., 2014; Albert et al., 2015, 2016; Bergantz et
42 al., 2015; Trua and Marani, 2021). Olivine crystals provide information on the mantle source and
43 the different crustal storage conditions (close vs. open-system) prior to eruption (e.g.,
44 Danyushevsky et al., 2002; Sakyi et al., 2012; Gavrilenko et al., 2016). Furthermore, Fe-Mg
45 diffusion chronometry of zoned olivine crystals can provide the timescales of the pre-eruptive

46 processes (e.g., Hartley et al., 2016; Schleicher et al., 2016; Pankhurst et al., 2018; Albert et al.,
47 2019, 2020).

48 We examine olivine crystals from basic lavas erupted at the back-arc submarine Marsili
49 Volcano (MV), an active volcano in the Southern Tyrrhenian Sea with potential tsunami hazard
50 (Fig. 1; see the Data Repository for details on the geological setting). The variability found in the
51 MV olivine offers an opportunity to investigate the magmatic processes, and their timescales,
52 occurring in a mush-dominated back-arc plumbing system. In active volcanic areas, this
53 variability has direct implications on the geophysical and geochemical signals recorded by the
54 monitoring agencies (e.g. Hartley et al., 2016; Pankhurst et al., 2018; Albert et al., 2019).
55 Therefore, a better understanding of the ongoing processes below the volcano and their
56 timescales will improve the interpretation of the monitoring data.

57 **THE HETEROGENEOUS PLUMBING SYSTEM OF THE MARSILI VOLCANO**

58 The available petrological data for the MV lavas provide a detailed record of the
59 polybaric crystallization that occurred within a vertically extended crustal plumbing system
60 made of stacked and interconnected melt- and crystal-rich mush zones. The major phases
61 involved in the crystallization processes are olivine, clinopyroxene and late plagioclase. Previous
62 studies suggest that the magmatic system varies from clinopyroxene-rich to amphibole-bearing
63 lithologies at the near-Moho horizon, while a more felsic plagioclase-rich framework dominates
64 the mid to uppermost crustal levels (Trua et al., 2014, 2018; Trua and Marani, 2021).

65 **SAMPLES AND METHODS**

66 We have considered 12 samples (Fig. 1), representing the compositional range of the MV
67 basic lavas (Trua et al., 2018). The lavas were dredged from the deep northern sector (MRS1,
68 MRS2, and MRS4 basalts), the spreading axis (D5 and D6 basalts, and D1, D2 and D4 basaltic

69 andesites), and the south-eastern flank (D12 and D16 basalts, and D11 and D19 basaltic
70 andesites). From the 12 samples we have selected seven containing zoned olivine crystals (as
71 single crystals or in glomerocrysts) suitable for diffusion modelling (MRS1, MRS4, D4, D5, D6,
72 D12 and D16). We have modelled 28 Fe–Mg concentration gradients using the DIPRA code
73 (Girona and Costa, 2013). Olivine compositions and crystallographic axes were determined
74 according to standard Electron Probe Microanalyzer (EPMA) and Electron Backscatter
75 Diffraction (EBSD) procedures. Details about analytical methods and the diffusion modelling
76 approach can be found in the Data Repository.

77 **TIMESCALES OF OPEN-SYSTEM PROCESSES IN A HETEROGENEOUS MUSH-** 78 **DOMINATED PLUMBING SYSTEM**

79 Three types of olivine populations can be recognized, each linked to a distinct pre-
80 eruptive scenario as discussed below.

81 **Sampling a crystal-rich mush layer**

82 The first type of olivine refers to the crystals carried in basaltic (D5) and basaltic andesite
83 (D4) lavas erupted at the MV axis portion (Fig. 1). Both eruptions were fed by a magma derived
84 from the mafic mush region located at the base of the MV crust (Trua et al., 2018; Trua and
85 Marani, 2021).

86 The olivine cargo in sample D5 contains the largest range of forsterite mol% [$Fo = 100 \times$
87 $Mg/(Mg + Fe)$] core compositions (Fo₇₇₋₉₀) with crystals exhibiting normal, reverse and
88 complex zoning patterns, and sometimes virtually unzoned (Figs. 2 and 3A). We interpret that
89 the olivine core compositions are documenting the variations of the intensive variables (e.g.,
90 temperature and/or fO_2 ; Albert et al., 2020) and melt composition along the crystal mush.
91 Crystals do not share a common rim composition; therefore, we exclude a re-equilibration with

92 the carrier melt after the mush disaggregation (e.g., Neave et al., 2013). Instead, we propose that
93 crystals interacted with intruding melts responsible for remobilizing the crystal-mush in multiple
94 episodes of rejuvenation (Latypov and Egorova, 2012; Brahm et al., 2018). Assuming the
95 hypothetical homogeneity of the rising melt, after reaching and percolating into the mush its
96 composition might have locally changed by resorbing and cannibalizing antecrysts, thus
97 promoting the growth of rims with different compositions.

98 We have calculated four timescales of 1.2-1.6 years (regardless the Fo content or the
99 zoning pattern), one timescale of 0.6 years and one of 9 years (Figs. 2 and 3B). Such a variety of
100 olivine compositions, zoning patterns and timescales is recording the presence of micro-domains,
101 with local conditions and interactions, inside the deep crystal-rich mush region.

102 The D4 olivine crystals exhibit more evolved compositions compared to the D5 crystals
103 (Figs. 2 and 3A), with Fo₇₂₋₇₃ core values and reversely zoned towards Fo₇₆. Hence, D4
104 olivine crystallized in a more evolved melt prior to be collected by the carrier magma. According
105 to the record preserved in the coexisting clinopyroxene (Trua and Marani, 2021), the magma
106 feeding D4 was stored in the upper part of the mush pile as the result of a late fractionation stage
107 of the melt extracted from the underlying levels (and similar to D5 in composition). The most
108 suitable olivine crystals to be modelled (i.e. those with homogeneous profile and constant rim
109 composition) yield times of 1.2 to 1.6 years, while crystals that had to be modelled as a step
110 function returned times of 2.3 and 3.3 years (Fig. 3B). In general, the D4 crystals are relatively
111 homogeneous in composition and diffusion times compared to sample D5. Only few crystals
112 from D4 reveal more complex histories due to the existence of different microdomains also in
113 the upper part of the crystal-mush.

114 Even if D5 and D4 correspond to the lower and upper parts of the mush pile, respectively,
115 their olivine crystals yield comparable timescales, indicating that disaggregation of the deep MV
116 mush zone occurred over a timescale of few years prior to the eruption.

117 **Rapid ascent of deep magma and, eventually, interception of shallow magma pockets**

118 The second type of olivine refers to the crystals carried in the basaltic lavas erupted in the
119 MV northern sector (MRS samples; Fig. 1). While plagioclase crystals record shallow storage
120 conditions, likely in small and melt-rich magma pockets (Trua et al., 2018), olivine exhibits high
121 and narrow Fo composition (cores with Fo88-90 for MRS2 and MRS4, Fo84-86 for MRS1; Figs.
122 1C and 3A). This is coupled with a large Ca concentration range (e.g. De Hoog et al., 2010) that
123 arises from the variability in the primary melt compositions present during crystallization, thus
124 attesting a deeper origin within the plumbing system.

125 The MRS olivine crystals are virtually unzoned or normally zoned towards Fo83-84. We
126 have modelled four normally zoned crystals from MRS1 and MRS4 basalts, and we have
127 obtained three timescales of few days (≤ 17 days; MRS1-ol7 and MRS4-ol3 and ol4; Fig. 3B)
128 consistent with a rapid ascent of the carrier magma. One bigger crystal (MRS1-ol-8) yielded a
129 timescale of ≈ 8 years, likely representing a different antecryst population that resided for a
130 longer period in the magmatic system. However, this crystal population has not been studied in
131 detail. The MRS2 basalt contains virtually unzoned primitive olivine (Fo88-90). We interpret the
132 absence of Fo zoning as rapid magma ascent without interaction with melts stalled in the crust.
133 Overall, the MRS- crystal record supports a rapid migration through the MV crust of the carrier
134 magma and, eventually, the interception of shallower magma pockets containing plagioclase.

135 **Mixing between multiple crystal- and melt-rich mush zones**

136 The third type of olivine refers to crystals carried in basalts sampled at the south-eastern
137 flank (D12 and D16) and the axis portion (D6) (Fig. 1). Olivine crystals from these basalts can
138 be grouped based on their Fo core (87-72) compositions and zoning patterns (normal, reverse
139 and complex; Figs. 1C and 3A).

140 By modelling the diffusion profiles, we have identified timescales clustering at ≈ 1 -2
141 months and timescales ranging from ≈ 0.5 to 3 years (Fig. 3B). We interpret these samples as the
142 result of multiple magma mixing during melt migration and interception of crystal- and melt-rich
143 mush pockets stalled in the crust. The glomeroporphyritic and dissolution textures of plagioclase
144 (Trua et al., 2018) and clinopyroxene (Trua and Marani, 2021) along with the variety of olivine
145 populations (based on composition and zoning patterns) support this interpretation.

146 **GENERAL DISCUSSION AND CONCLUDING REMARKS**

147 We have considered different eruptions from the same volcanic system providing new
148 and valuable data that helps understanding the heterogeneities intrinsic of a mush-dominated
149 system. Olivine crystals from the MV preserve key geochemical features of the different open-
150 system processes occurring within the heterogeneous and complex mush plumbing system
151 beneath the volcano (Fig. 4). We have constrained the timescales of three different crustal
152 scenarios: (1) timescales gradually decreasing from nine to nearly one year representing the
153 disaggregation of the deep mush zone; (2) timescales of days for rapidly ascending mantle
154 magmas in a nearly solidified transcrustal mush domain; and (3) timescales clustered in two
155 groups of ca. 1-2 months and 0.5 to 3 years indicating magma mixing events between crystal-
156 and melt-rich mush zones prior to eruption.

157 Our study contributes to the understanding of the conditions of accretion and crustal
158 storage of mantle-derived basaltic melts in a crystal mush environment. Scenario one takes place

159 in an eruptible crystal-rich mush region, scenario two is related to a nearly solidified mush
160 domain with a more fragile behavior allowing fast transport of mantle magma through dykes
161 and, scenario three corresponds to a moderately crystal-rich sector spotted with melt-rich pockets
162 (Fig. 4). The three identified scenarios can be linked to different rheological properties along
163 with local variations in the stress field of the crust and provides new information for future
164 numerical models replicating the behavior of the crust during magma ascent in different tectonic
165 settings. The comparison between the timescales calculated from diffusion modelling along with
166 the unrest data in basaltic volcanoes from different tectonic settings as Paricutin (Albert et al.,
167 2020), Etna (e.g. Kahl et al., 2011), Piton de la Fournaise (e.g. Albert et al., 2019) and Canary
168 Island monogenetic eruptions (e.g. Albert et al., 2015) highlights the variability of the unrest
169 periods. Variations of the unrest timescales in a composite volcano or in a monogenetic volcanic
170 region hinder the management of the volcanic crisis. For example, the unrest preceding the 2021
171 eruption of La Palma (Canary Islands) followed the most frequent timescales of ca. few years,
172 few months and few days proposed by Albert et al. (2016) for monogenetic eruptions; while the
173 previous eruption of Teneguía (La Palma, 1971) had a shorter unrest (about one month). This
174 scenario of varying unrest patterns becomes more plausible in areas where the plumbing system
175 is dominated by a transcrustal mush system like in the MV.

176 We highlight the importance of comprehensively studying samples that represent
177 different parts of the mush system in order to build a whole picture of the plumbing system
178 architecture and its timescales. This will lead to a better interpretation of monitoring data in
179 active volcanic areas characterized by the presence of a mush region, where different unrest
180 behaviors and different eruptive scenarios can occur according to the local variability of melt
181 supply conditions.

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190

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296 **Figure 1.** (A) Location of the back-arc Vavilov (VB) and Marsili (MB) Basins and Tyrrhenian
 297 Sea (TS) in the inset. The main figure displays the bathymetric map of the Marsili Volcano. Lava
 298 samples are classified according to their location (blue, green and orange dots). (B) SiO₂ (wt%)
 299 against FeO_{tot}/MgO ratio for the Marsili lavas (grey field; data from Trua et al., 2018). In bold
 300 the samples with olivine profiles selected for diffusion chronometry. (C) Forsterite (Fo) versus
 301 Ca in olivine crystals. The black arrows indicate the effects of fractionation, slow Ca diffusion

302 and magmatic H₂O dehydration or entry (Gavrilenko et al., 2016). In the inset, the black field
303 shows the compositions of olivine crystallizing at the surface from primary melts of anhydrous
304 peridotite. The high magnesian olivine (Fo₈₉₋₉₀) crystallized from primary melts of hydrous
305 peridotite have lower Ca content than those from anhydrous systems, as illustrated by the
306 subduction related olivine from the Aeolian Arc (data from Zamboni et al., 2017); brown field)
307 and the Irazu Volcano (data from Ruprecht and Plank, 2013); orange field). The grey field for
308 mantle olivine is based on data from Sobolev et al. (2009) and De Hoog et al. (2010). The
309 analyzed olivine crystals erupted at different sites on the MV exhibit a compositional range, in
310 terms of Ca versus Fo, that overlaps the distribution observed in the nearby Aeolian arc basic
311 lavas and record as much variation as primary magmas.

312 **Figure 2.** Forsterite (Fo) profiles and diffusion modelling from the crystal mush sample (D5;
313 green shadow area) and from its upper zone (D4; purple shadow area). Sample D5 displays
314 higher Fo values and more zoning-type variations compared to D4 accordingly to the presence of
315 mush horizons formed by solidification of basic magmas where the more primitive crystals can
316 be found in the lower part of the mush pile and the more evolved ones in the upper zone (e.g.,
317 Costa et al., 2010; Hartley et al., 2016; Pankhurst et al., 2018). Lighter and wider lines indicate
318 de analytical data, while darker and thinner over-imposed lines correspond to the modelled
319 profiles. Calculated timescales and acronym of each crystal are indicated in the legend.

320 **Figure 3.** (A) Olivine profiles from the three possible scenarios. In light grey all the analyzed
321 profiles. (B) Timescales distribution of each sample representing the three different scenarios
322 (see the main text for further discussion). Calculated diffusion times are plotted as diamonds
323 (error bars are reported as grey lines) and each olivine number is written next to it (Table S2
324 Data Repository).

325 **Figure 4.** General schematic model of a heterogeneous mush-dominated plumbing system
326 beneath a volcano. Possible pre-eruptive interactions between the ascending magma and the
327 melt- and/or crystal-rich zones are indicated for the three scenarios along with the timescales of
328 the open-system processes.

329

330 ¹GSA Data Repository item 201Xxxx (geological setting, analytical methods, thermobarometric
331 conditions and details on the diffusion modelling) is available online at
332 www.geosociety.org/pubs/ft20XX.htm, or on request from editing@geosociety.org.